

The charge carrier mobilities of hybrid perovskite transistors reported in H. Zhu *et al.*, *Nat. Commun.* **13**, 1741 (2022) DOI: 10.1038/s41467-022-29434-x appear to be severely overestimated (by at least a factor of 4 in transistors and a factor of ~ 670 in Hall-effect measurements) as the result of misinterpreted transistor characteristics, the use of significantly underestimated gate-channel capacitance, and apparently faulty Hall effect measurements.*

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The charge carrier mobilities, μ , of hybrid perovskite thin-film transistors (TFTs) reported by H. Zhu *et al.*¹ are found to be grossly overestimated. The actual mobility of the best device (stated to be fabricated “via rational halide anion (I/Br/Cl) engineering”), correctly calculated from the published data, is in the range $\mu_{\text{sat}} = 3.6 - 4.88 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$, not $20 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ claimed by the authors. In addition, our analysis of the reported Hall effect results obtained in ungated thin films of the same (optimized) composition, shows that the Hall carrier concentration reported by the authors is underestimated by a factor of ~ 670 (compared to the carrier density determined from the electrical TFT data). Apparently, this explains the severely overestimated Hall mobility of $\mu_{\text{Hall}} = 301 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ reported in this paper. Our conclusion is that the main claims of this paper regarding the realization of “high-performance perovskite transistors” with the stated mobilities appears to be misleading.

The following device parameters are used by the authors (as given in the paper):

Channel width, $W = 1000 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$;

Channel length, $L = 150 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$;

Capacitance per unit area of an ALD-grown HfO_2 gate dielectric used by the authors, $C_i = 270 \text{ nF/cm}^2$;

Thickness of HfO_2 layer, $d_{\text{ox}} = 40 \text{ nm}$;

Thickness of the perovskite films: $t = 40 \text{ nm}$.

Other parameters used in our analysis below:

The static dielectric constant of ALD-grown HfO_2 is $\epsilon = 25$.² Thus, the actual gate-channel capacitance per unit area of a 40 nm-thick HfO_2 is $C_i = \epsilon\epsilon_0/d_{\text{ox}} = 553 \text{ nF/cm}^2$ ($\epsilon_0 = 8.85 \times 10^{-12} \text{ F/m}$ is the permittivity of free space). *The authors have not provided any reasoning for the use of a highly underestimated C_i . Neither the main text nor Supplementary contain any characterization of the dielectric properties or capacitance of the gate dielectric layer.*

1. The best performing TFT said to be fabricated “via rational halide anion (I/Br/Cl) engineering” (Fig. 1b in H. Zhu *et al.*, red curve in the 4th panel).¹ The authors report that this device exhibits the highest saturation regime mobility of $\mu_{\text{sat}} = 20 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$. Below, we have digitized this curve and analyzed it.

The Fig. below shows this transfer curve replotted on a semi-log scale:

The best performing TFT device, Fig. 1b (panel 4, the red curve)

Another Fig. below shows the same data re-plotted as a linear $|I_{DS}|^{0.5}(V_{GS})$ plot (open red squares), with a linear fit in the range $-12V < V_{GS} < 0$ shown by the green line. The average slope of this curve is $\delta(|I_{DS}|^{0.5})/\delta V_{GS} = 0.003 \text{ A}^{0.5}/V$ (green line). We used this slope to calculate the saturation mobility of this TFT according to the standard Shockley equation,³ which has also been used by H. Zhu *et al.*:

$$\mu_{\text{sat}} = \frac{2L}{WC_i} \cdot \left(\frac{\partial \sqrt{|I_{\text{DS}}|}}{\partial V_{\text{GS}}} \right)^2.$$

As one can see from the formula for μ_{sat} above, calculation of the mobility depends on the used gate-channel capacitance, C_i . Below we have calculated μ_{sat} using (1) an underestimated capacitance $C_i = 270 \text{ nF/cm}^2$ used by the authors, and (2) the correct capacitance of a 40 nm-thick HfO_2 , $C_i = 553 \text{ nF/cm}^2$:

(1) Using the underestimated $C_i = 270 \text{ nF/cm}^2$ and the slope above, we obtain $\mu_{\text{sat}} \approx 10 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$.

(2) Using the correct capacitance $C_i = 553 \text{ nF/cm}^2$ and the same slope, we obtain $\mu_{\text{sat}} \approx 4.88 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$.

Thus, one can see that even with the underestimated capacitance used by the authors, the mobility turns out to be *twice lower* than the value reported by the authors. By using the correct capacitance, however, one arrives to a value smaller than the reported one by a factor of ~ 4 .

2. We now turn to the $|I_{\text{DS}}|^{0.5}(V_{\text{GS}})$ plot of the same (best performing) device included by the authors in the Supplementary file (Supplementary Fig. 4 in H. Zhu *et al.*).¹ The Fig. below shows this plot, with the black straight line drawn by the authors to indicate the slope (left panel), and our analysis of the slope (right panel).

The slope of this curve is $\delta(|I_{DS}|^{0.5})/\delta V_{GS} = 2.573 \times 10^{-3} \text{ A}^{0.5}/\text{V}$ (dashed green line or solid black line). We can thus calculate the saturation regime mobility μ_{sat} from this graph using the other device parameters given in the paper (stated above) and the above formula for μ_{sat} .

(1) Using the underestimated $C_i = 270 \text{ nF/cm}^2$, we obtain $\mu_{sat} \approx 7.35 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$.

(2) Using the correct capacitance $C_i = 553 \text{ nF/cm}^2$ and the same slope, we obtain $\mu_{sat} \approx 3.6 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$.

Thus, the analysis in Sections 1 and 2 above shows that the actual mobility of the best-performing TFT in this paper is in the range $\mu_{sat} = 3.6 - 4.88 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$, which is a factor of 4 - 5.5 smaller than the mobility reported by the authors for this TFT.

3. Apparently faulty Hall effect measurement are reported in H. Zhu *et al.*¹ A careful look at the results of the Hall-effect measurement of (ungated) perovskite films of the optimized composition (those with the “rational halide anion (I/Br/Cl) engineering”) clearly shows that the Hall carrier density, n_{Hall} , is severely underestimated, while the corresponding Hall mobility, μ_{Hall} , is severely overestimated.

Indeed, the authors stated that for the best performing composition (that is, the “I/Br/Cl” film), they have obtained $n_{Hall, 3D} = 2.2 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ (note, this is a 3D concentration) and $\mu_{Hall} = 301 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$.

We then conducted Hall-effect measurements to investigate the carrier concentrations and Hall mobilities of the perovskite films, which are important for understanding the performance of the resulting TFTs. As shown in Fig. 2d, the I-pristine films exhibited an average hole concentration of $2.8 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, which gradually decreased to 6.9×10^{16} , 4.5×10^{16} , and $2.2 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ for the I/Br, I/Cl, and I/Br/Cl films, respectively. This trend resulted from

The Hall mobilities (μ_{Hall}) of the perovskite films showed a consistent trend with the μ_{FE} extracted from the corresponding TFTs, with the average μ_{Hall} increasing from $25 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (I-pristine) to 57 (I/Br) and $92 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (I/Cl), respectively. The μ_{Hall} for I/Br/Cl films was up to $301 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. According to the

Besides Hall effect measurements, the density of mobile carriers in thin films can be determined from the onset voltage, V_{onset} , of the corresponding TFTs (that is, a positive gate voltage necessary to deplete holes from the entire thin film and drastically reduce its conductivity).⁴⁻⁶ The optimized TFT shown above (see the plots in sections 1 and 2) has the onset voltage of about $V_{\text{onset}} \approx 1.7$ V, and, thus, the projected (areal) carrier density in the perovskite film is:

$$n_{\text{TFT},2\text{D}} = e^{-1} C_i V_{\text{onset}} = 5.88 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2}.$$

The projected (areal) carrier density can be converted to the 3D (volume) density by dividing the former by the thickness of the perovskite film ($t = 40$ nm):

$$n_{\text{TFT},3\text{D}} = n_{\text{TFT},2\text{D}}/t = 1.47 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}.$$

Apparently, there is a huge, nearly 3-orders-of-magnitude, disagreement between the Hall measurements and the electrical (TFT) measurements in terms of the carrier concentration. More precisely, the Hall and TFT results on the carrier density disagree by a factor of:

$$\frac{n_{\text{TFT},3\text{D}}}{n_{\text{Hall},3\text{D}}} \cong 670.$$

Note, n_{TFT} value above has been obtained by using the correct capacitance $C_i = 553$ nF/cm² of the gate dielectric (40 nm-thick HfO₂). Even if we used the underestimated capacitance used by the authors, n_{TFT} would decrease only by a factor of ~ 2 . This **gaping inconsistency** is too great to be remedied by possible mistakes in device parameters.

Correspondingly, the Hall carrier mobility, μ_{Hall} , reported by the authors is dramatically overestimated (by a similar factor). This is because n_{Hall} and μ_{Hall} in the Hall-effect measurements are always mutually related through the equation: $\sigma = e \times n_{\text{Hall}} \times \mu_{\text{Hall}}$.⁷⁻⁹ **Thus, the reported $\mu_{\text{Hall}} = 301 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ is overestimated by a factor of ~ 670 , which suggests that the actual μ_{Hall} must be about $0.45 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$.** The latter value makes sense in comparison with the TFT mobility $\mu_{\text{sat}} \sim 4 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ estimated above, as it is well known that in polycrystalline materials, the Hall effect is expected to lead to a Hall mobility smaller than the TFT mobility due to the effect of grain boundaries.¹⁰

We emphasize that the discrepancy between μ_{Hall} and μ_{TFT} revealed by our analysis above cannot be rationalized by possible differences between the efficiencies of the bulk and surface charge transport. Indeed, the only parameter directly obtained from the Hall-effect measurements is the charge carrier concentration, not the mobility.⁷⁻⁹ The Hall mobility is calculated as $\mu_{\text{Hall}} = \sigma/(e \cdot n_{\text{Hall}})$. Given the absence of any experimental details or raw data on the Hall measurements in H. Zhu *et al.*,¹ we cannot speculate regarding the possible origin of this huge error.

4. Finally, there is also an obvious (at least, an order of magnitude) inconsistency in the conductivities of (ungated) perovskite films reported in this paper. Indeed, using the mobility correctly estimated from the TFT characteristics of the hero device ($\mu_{\text{sat}} = 4.88 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$) and the corresponding film's carrier density determined from the depleting onset voltage of the same device ($n_{\text{TFT},2\text{D}} = 5.88 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2}$), one can estimate the sheet conductivity (per square) of this perovskite film in its ungated state:

$$\sigma_{\text{film}} = e \cdot n_{\text{TFT},2\text{D}} \cdot \mu_{\text{sat}} = 4.6 \times 10^{-6} \text{ S}/\square.$$

However, from the results of the Hall measurements reported by the authors for the same film ($n_{\text{Hall, 3D}} = 2.2 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and $\mu_{\text{Hall}} = 301 \text{ cm}^2 \text{V}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$), one obtains:

$$\sigma_{\text{film}} = e \cdot (n_{\text{Hall,3D}} \times t) \cdot \mu_{\text{Hall}} = 4.24 \times 10^{-7} \text{ S}/\square.$$

CONCLUSION:

The charge carrier mobilities of hybrid perovskite TFTs reported in H. Zhu *et al.*¹ appear to be severely exaggerated. The correctly calculated TFT mobilities are $\mu_{\text{sat}} \sim 3.6 - 4.88 \text{ cm}^2 \text{V}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$, which means that the reported mobilities are overestimated by a factor of $\sim 4 - 5$. The reported Hall effect results are wrong by a factor of ~ 670 (the Hall carrier density is severely underestimated, while the Hall mobility is severely overestimated).

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